

The effects of mammalian hormones in the regulation of growth and virulence in *Campylobacter jejuni*

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Summary

Campylobacter jejuni is the most common cause of bacterial food borne disease, but studies on its pathogenesis are still limited. The effects of various mammalian hormones such as, norepinephrine, epinephrine, serotonin, corticosterone, cortisol and cortisone on growth and different virulence mechanisms of *Campylobacter* were reported previously.

In this study, the possible effects of norepinephrine, melatonin, estradiol, progesterone and insulin on growth, adhesion and invasion of *C. jejuni* were investigated in human adenocarcinoma colon cell (HT-29) line. Moreover, the alterations on biofilm formation on abiotic surfaces and response to stress conditions were investigated. We also aimed to analyze the effects of hormones and *C. jejuni*, together or separately, on viability of human adenocarcinoma colon (HT-29) cells. Growth alterations were determined spectrophotometrically. Adhesive/invasive bacterial counts

were evaluated by colony counting method. Biofilm formation was analyzed using a microtiter plate assay. The alterations of HT-29 cell viability were determined via methyl thiazolyl diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide assay.

According to our results, growth of *C. jejuni* was decreased in the presence of hormones in a dose and time-dependent manner ($p < 0.05$). Each hormone at all concentrations reduced the adhesion of bacteria ($p < 0.0001$). The invasion of *C. jejuni* was increased in the presence of progesterone and insulin at all concentrations; which were statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). The effects of hormones on biofilm formation were variable. Hormones did not affect *C. jejuni* growth in oxidative and nitrosative conditions ($p > 0.05$). Each hormone and *C. jejuni* infection have separately decreased the viability of cells after 24 hours incubation ($p < 0.005$). In 48 hours, viability of cells was significantly increased in the presence of low-level estradiol ($p < 0.0001$) and high-level progesterone ($p < 0.0005$). The hormones were found to be significantly more effective on viability of infected HT-29 cells than non-infected cells.

In conclusions, these findings once more showed that hormones affect *C. jejuni* during infectious processes.

Key words

Campylobacter jejuni, mammalian hormones, growth, adhesion-invasion, colon cell, biofilm

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1. Introduction

Since it was shown that microorganisms have receptors for insulin and estradiol as well as for other neuroendocrine hormones, researchers are interested for "microbial endocrinology" to explain biological processes between host hormones and microorganisms during an infection.^{1,2} It was shown that when a microorganism enters the host, host conditions including hormones have become the microbe's environment.¹⁻⁴ Like all environmental factors, hormones (dopamine, epinephrine, norepinephrine, melatonin, serotonin, estradiol, estrogen, progesterone, testosterone and insulin, etc.) also found to regulate microbe's behaviors such as growth, metabolic processes, virulence mechanisms, gene expressions, antimicrobial susceptibilities.^{1,3-9}

Campylobacter jejuni is the most common cause of bacterial food borne disease in many developed countries.^{10,11} Although its' infections are seen frequently, studies on the pathogenesis are still limited.

According to our knowledge, the effects of various mammalian hormones such as, norepinephrine, epinephrine, serotonin, corticosterone, cortisol and cortisone on growth and different virulence mechanisms of *Campylobacter* were reported previously.^{8,12} In this concept, the one of the objectives of this study was to evaluate the effects of norepinephrine (NE), melatonin (MEL), estradiol (EST), progesterone (PRO) and insulin (INS) on the growth, adhesion and invasion of *C. jejuni* in human adenocarcinoma colon cell (HT-29) culture as an infection model. On the other hand, the effects of host hormones on biofilm formation on abiotic surfaces and growth abilities of *C. jejuni* in oxidative (in the presence of hydrogen peroxide, H₂O₂) and nitrosative (in the presence of nitrosating agent sodium nitroprusside, SNP) stress conditions were also evaluated. In the meantime, we aimed to determine the effects of hormones and *C. jejuni*, together or separately, on viability of human adenocarcinoma colon cells (HT-29).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Bacterium, medium, and hormones

In this study, we used a *Campylobacter jejuni* strain 81116 which was kindly provided by Dr. György Schneider, (University of Pécs, Hungary). *C. jejuni* was grown in Brucella broth (BB) (Besimik, Turkey) under microaerophilic conditions at 37°C for 48 hours.

We evaluated the effects of each hormone at two concentrations according to their psychological levels of blood in a healthy person [NE (0.0017 and 0.04µg/mL), MEL (6 and 60 pg/mL), EST (0.1 and 0.4 ng/mL), PRO (2 and 20 ng/mL) and INS (20 and 200 µIU/mL)] to mimic *in vivo* conditions of host.

2.2. Cell culture

Human colon adenocarcinoma cell line (HT-29) (91072201-1VL, Sigma-Aldrich) was used in these experiments. The cell line was cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (DMEM) (Sigma, 5546) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Biowest, S1810-500), 1% 2mM L-glutamine (Biological Industries, BI03-020-1B) and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (50 IU/ml penicillin and 50µg/ml streptomycin; Biological Industries, 03-031-1B) and were seeded in plates according to assays. We used HT-29 cells in growth, adhesion, invasion and cell viability assays in the presence/absence of hormones.

The (human colon adenocarcinoma) cells were incubated (37°C, 24 hours, 5 % CO₂) to provide a confluent monolayer cell culture. The 96-well microplates (1×10⁴ seeding density each well) were used for bacterial growth and methyl thiazolyl diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide (MTT) assays for cell viability. While, for bacterial adhesion and invasion experiments, 24-well plates (5 × 10⁴ seeding density each well) were used.

2.3. Infection of human adenocarcinoma (HT-29 line) cells

Before inoculating *C. jejuni*, medium supplemented with antibiotics was removed from the cell culture, and antimicrobial solution-free DMEM and hormones were added into the each well (20µL for each well/96-well plates and 50 µL for each well/24-well plates) and the plates were incubated at 37°C for 1 hour before growth, adhesion, invasion and cell viability assays. *C. jejuni* was inoculated and incubated in Brucella broth at 37°C for 24 hours for overnight culture. Cells were infected with an initial suspension of approximately 10⁹ CFU/mL of *C. jejuni* then incubated at 37°C under microaerophilic conditions in different periods according to assay.

2.4. Bacterial growth

Infected cells with *C. jejuni* incubated in the presence/absence of hormones along with two- four- and 24 h periods for detecting alterations of growth. The effects of each hormone concentration on bacterial growth were determined by measuring the changes in absorbance at 600 nm. The absorbance results of infected HT-29 cell culture with/without hormones were compared. The experiments were repeated three times independently and all conditions were analyzed thrice.

2.5. Bacterial adhesion and invasion

Infected cells with *C. jejuni* were incubated in the presence/absence of hormones at 37°C for three hours under microaerophilic conditions.

Following the adhesion and invasion assay's stages (mentioned below), the effects of each hormone at all concentrations were detected by comparing colony counts (as CFU/mL) obtained from cell lysates of cell cultures with and without hormones. The colony counts of adhesive and invasive bacteria were determined as described previously.^{13,14} All conditions were examined in triplicate and each experiment was performed thrice.

2.5.1. Bacterial adhesion

After incubation for three hours as mentioned above, infected HT-29 cells in wells were washed three times with phosphate buffer saline (PBS) to remove unbound bacteria and treated with 500µl 1% Triton X-100 to lyse the cells for 10 minutes at 37°C under 5% CO₂ conditions. The real number of adhered-bacteria was detected by colony counting method. We homogenized the cell lysates and inoculated on Mueller–Hinton agar (MHA) (Spesera, Turkey) supplemented with 5% defibrinated sheep blood and incubated at 37°C for 48 hours under microaerophilic conditions.

2.5.2. Bacterial invasion

Following incubation at three hours as mentioned above, infected HT-29 cells in wells were washed with PBS three times and a fresh medium containing 300 ng/ml gentamicin was added to kill extracellular bacteria and plates were incubated at 37°C for two hours under microaerophilic conditions. Then, HT-29 cells were lysed with Triton X-100 and for quantification of invasive bacteria, cell lysates were homogenized and inoculated as mentioned above.

2.6. Bacterial biofilm formation

We used microtiter plate assay to detect biofilm formation. The 96-well plates inoculated with 20µL *C. je-*

juni (approximately 10^8 CFU/mL), 80 μ L BB and 100 μ L of each hormone at different concentrations were incubated at 37°C for 48 h under microaerophilic conditions.

After incubation, we aspirated the contents from wells gently and washed them three times with PBS to remove unattached bacteria and dried at 60°C for 30 min. To fixate the attached bacteria methanol was added to each well and incubated for 15 min, the contents of the wells were aspirated.

For detecting biofilm formation, it was added 1% crystal violet into each well to stain the biofilms and the plates were incubated at room temperature for 30 minutes. After the aspiration of the dye gently, the wells were washed with distilled water twice, the plates were dried at 37°C. The crystal violet was dissolved by 20% acetone added ethanol in each well for 15 min at room temperature.

Biofilm formations were detected by optical density measurement in a spectrophotometer at 570 nm.¹⁵ In this assay, *E. coli* ATCC 25922 (a biofilm-forming strain) was used as positive control and un-inoculated BB without hormones was used as negative control. All experimental conditions were analyzed three times.

2.7. Bacterial growth in oxidative and nitrosative stress conditions

To determine the effects of hormones on growth of *C. jejuni* in oxidative and nitrosative stress conditions, overnight cultures of bacteria were cultured in BB with/without hormones at different concentrations and incubated at 37°C for 48 hours under microaerophilic condition.¹⁶ After we spread 100 μ L bacterial suspensions onto MHA supplemented with 5% defibrinated sheep blood, sterile filter discs containing hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) at different concentrations (1 mM, 10 mM, 100 mM and 1 M) for oxidative stress and sterile filter discs containing nitrosating agent sodium nitroprusside (SNP) at different concentrations (10 μ M, 20 μ M, 40 μ M and 80 μ M) for nitrosative stress were placed onto each plate and the plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 hours under microaerophilic condition.^{17,18} After incubation, the diameters of inhibition zones around discs containing H₂O₂ and SNP were measured. All conditions were analyzed independently two times, each experiment was replicated twice.

2.8 Human colon adenocarcinoma cell (HT-29) viability

To determine the effects of hormones and *C. jejuni*, together or separately, on viability of human adenocarcinoma colon cells (HT-29), after cell culture was

incubated for 1 hour in 96 well plates with/without hormones. Then overnight cultured *C. jejuni* (10^9 CFU/ml) were inoculated and incubated at 37°C along with 24 and 48 hour periods under microaerophilic conditions.

After each incubation period, it was washed the wells three times with PBS to remove all residues. Fresh culture medium and methyl thiazolyl diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide (12 mM, Neofrox 3580 MTT) prepared as described by Mosmann (1983) was added into each well.¹⁹ The plates were further incubated for 4 hours at 37°C under microaerophilic conditions. We aspirated the content from wells and remained formosan crystals in wells were dissolved by adding dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) for 10 minutes. Absorbance was measured at 540 nm via the spectrophotometric method. All experimental conditions were tested in triplicate and each experiment was performed thrice.

2.9. Statistical analysis

The significant differences between experimental conditions and control conditions were analyzed. Statistical analysis was carried out using two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's and Sidak's multiple comparisons test for growth alterations and cell viability results, respectively. One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons test was used for the analysis of adhesion, invasion and biofilm results. All results were presented as mean \pm SD. Differences with p values less than 0.05 were considered as significant.

3. Results

3.1. Bacterial growth

After 2 hours incubation, the growth of *C. jejuni* was statistically significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased in the presence of all hormones at all concentrations except high-level progesterone. The reduction of *C. jejuni* growth in 4 hours incubation was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) for all hormones at all concentrations except low-level estradiol and progesterone.

However, the effects of hormones on growth of *C. jejuni* were surprisingly different in 24 hours. Although all hormones reduced the growth of bacteria, the decreasing was not statistically significant except high-level norepinephrine ($p < 0.05$) and insulin ($p < 0.01$) (Figure 1).

3.2. Bacterial adhesion

All tested hormones at all concentrations were shown to reduce the adhesion of *C. jejuni* which was statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). Moreover, the presence of

Figure 1 Effects of hormones on the growth of *C. jejuni* strain.
 HC: High concentration, LC: Low concentration, NE: Norepinephrine, MEL: Melatonin, EST: Estradiol, PRO: Progesterone, INS: Insulin
 HC NE: 0.04 µg/mL, LC NE: 0.0017 µg/mL, HC MEL:60 pg/mL, LC MEL: 6 pg/mL, HC EST: 0.4 ng/mL, LC EST: 0.1 ng/mL, HC PRO: 20 ng/mL, LC PRO: 2 ng/mL, HC INS 200 and LC INS: 20 µIU/mL
 The growth of *C. jejuni* in HT-29 cell culture with/without hormones were examined using two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons test *, **: Significant at p<0.05 level and p<0.01 level values, respectively.

Figure 2

Effects of hormones on adhesion of *C. jejuni* strain.
 HC: High concentration, LC: Low concentration, NE: Norepinephrine, MEL: Melatonin, EST: Estradiol, PRO: Progesterone, INS: Insulin
 HC NE: 0.04 µg/mL, LC NE: 0.0017 µg/mL, HC MEL:60 pg/mL, LC MEL: 6 pg/mL, HC EST: 0.4 ng/mL, LC EST: 0.1 ng/mL, HC PRO: 20 ng/mL, LC PRO: 2 ng/mL, HC INS 200 and LC INS: 20 µIU/mL
 The adhesion of *C. jejuni* in HT-29 with/without hormones were examined using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons test ****: Significant at p <0.0001 level.

sex hormones at high-level concentrations and high and low-level concentrations of insulin have been found most effective on *C. jejuni* adhesion (Figure 2).

3.3. Bacterial invasion

The invasion ability of *C. jejuni* was enhanced in the presence of progesterone and insulin at high and low

concentrations; these results were statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). There was no statistically significant difference in the presence of other hormones ($p > 0.05$) (Figure 3).

3.4. Bacterial biofilm formation

Biofilm formation was statistically significantly decreased in the presence of norepinephrine at two levels and high level of estradiol; the highest inhibition was found in the presence of low-level norepinephrine. The increase of biofilm formation was found to

be statistically significant in the presence of progesterone at all concentrations ($p < 0.001$), melatonin ($p < 0.0001$) and insulin ($p < 0.005$) at low concentration (Figure 4).

3.5. Bacterial growth in oxidative and nitrosative stress conditions

All tested hormones at all concentrations did not affect the growth of *C. jejuni* in oxidative and nitrosative stress conditions ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 3

Effects of hormones on invasion ability of *C. jejuni* strain.

HC: High concentration, LC: Low concentration, NE: Norepinephrine, MEL: Melatonin, EST: Estradiol, PRO: Progesterone, INS: Insulin

HC NE: 0.04 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, LC NE: 0.0017 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, HC MEL: 60 pg/mL , LC MEL: 6 pg/mL , HC EST: 0.4 ng/mL , LC EST: 0.1 ng/mL , HC PRO: 20 ng/mL , LC PRO: 2 ng/mL , HC INS 200 and LC INS: 20 $\mu\text{IU/mL}$

The invasion of *C. jejuni* in HT-29 with/without hormones were examined using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons test ****: Significant at $p < 0.0001$ level.

Figure 4

Effects of hormones on biofilm formation of *C. jejuni* strain.

HC: High concentration, LC: Low concentration, NE: Norepinephrine, MEL: Melatonin, EST: Estradiol, PRO: Progesterone, INS: Insulin

HC NE: 0.04 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, LC NE: 0.0017 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, HC MEL: 60 pg/mL , LC MEL: 6 pg/mL , HC EST: 0.4 ng/mL , LC EST: 0.1 ng/mL , HC PRO: 20 ng/mL , LC PRO: 2 ng/mL , HC INS 200 and LC INS: 20 $\mu\text{IU/mL}$

The biofilm formation of *C. jejuni* with/without hormones were examined using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons test *, **, ****: Significant at $p < 0.05$ level, $p < 0.001$ and $p < 0.0001$ levels, respectively.

3.6. Human colon adenocarcinoma cell (HT-29) viability

The viability of HT-29 cells was shown to be decreased statistically significantly ($p < 0.005$) by each hormone, except high-level melatonin and progesterone, and *C. jejuni* infection in 24 hours incubation (Figure 5).

After 48 hours, the infection with *C. jejuni* caused to death of 0-13.3% HT-29 cells. We found that the viability of HT-29 cells was statistically significantly increased in the presence of low-level estradiol ($p < 0.0001$) and high-level progesterone ($p < 0.0005$) (Figure 5).

It was found that co-presence of bacteria and hormones (high-level norepinephrine, estradiol and progesterone; low-level melatonin and estradiol) increased the viability of HT-29 cells significantly ($p < 0.05$) at 24 hours incubation (Figure 6).

According to results of 48 hours incubation, co-presence of *C. jejuni* with high-level melatonin, estradiol and low-level norepinephrine, estradiol and insulin were found to enhance the viability of HT-29 cells ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 6).

4. Discussion

It is well known that host hormones not only regulate mammalian homeostasis but also affect microorganisms' behaviors involved in colonization, growth, expressions of genes for their metabolisms, virulence properties, and antimicrobial susceptibilities.^{1,3-9,20}

During the evolutionary progress, microorganisms recognize these hormones for adapting to host conditions. Today, there is a growing body of evidence about inter-kingdom signaling between microorganisms and hosts.^{1,2} Studies on microbial endocrinology provide new insights for understanding the biology of infections and the interactions between host-microbe via hormones.

In the previous studies, it has been reported that different hormones such as catecholamines, insulin and sex hormones increased and/or decreased the growth of pathogens such as *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Campylobacter jejuni*, *Helicobacter pylori*, *Bacteroides melanogenicus*, *Prevotella intermedius*, *Burkholderia pseudomallei* and *Candida albicans*.^{3-5,12,16,21-23} In general, the possible action mechanisms of hormones related to altering the growth of microorganisms can include iron, copper and zinc uptake (in metal-limited conditions), hormone-mediated induction of auto-inducers, acting as quorum sensing compounds such as homoserine lactones, indole and autoinducer-2,3), substitution of vitamin K, inhibition of enzymatic activation and membrane interactions.^{1,24,25}

Numerous studies showed that effects of insulin were variable on the growth of *S. aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *C. albicans*, *P. aeruginosa* and UPEC.^{4,21,22} Li et al.²⁶ have demonstrated that insulin receptor signaling pathways are defined as key contributors to colonization of *C. jejuni*. As an alternative perspective, in our study, the effects of hormones on *C. jejuni* were eval-

Figure 5

Effects of hormones, and *C. jejuni* infection on HT-29 cell viabilities..

HC: High concentration, LC: Low concentration, NE: Norepinephrine, MEL: Melatonin, EST: Estradiol, PRO: Progesterone, INS: Insulin

HC NE: 0.04 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, LC NE: 0.0017 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, HC MEL: 60 pg/mL , LC MEL: 6 pg/mL , HC EST: 0.4 ng/mL , LC EST: 0.1 ng/mL , HC PRO: 20 ng/mL , LC PRO: 2 ng/mL , HC INS 200 and LC INS: 20 $\mu\text{IU/mL}$

The cell viabilities in the presence of hormones at all concentrations and/or *C. jejuni* were analyzed using two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparisons test **, ***, ****: Significant at $p < 0.005$, $p < 0.0005$ and $p < 0.0001$ levels, respectively.

Figure 6

Effects of hormones and *C. jejuni* infection' co-presence on HT-29 cell viabilities.

HC: High concentration, LC: Low concentration, NE: Norepinephrine, MEL: Melatonin, EST: Estradiol, PRO: Progesterone, INS: Insulin

HC NE: 0.04 µg/mL, LC NE: 0.0017 µg/mL, HC MEL: 60 pg/mL, LC MEL: 6 pg/mL, HC EST: 0.4 ng/mL, LC EST: 0.1 ng/mL, HC PRO: 20 ng/mL, LC PRO: 2 ng/mL, HC INS 200 and LC INS: 20 µIU/mL

The cell viabilities with/without hormones at all concentrations were analyzed using two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparisons test *, **, ***, ****: Significant at $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.005$, $p < 0.0005$ and $p < 0.0001$ levels, respectively.

uated in cell culture to mimic *in-vivo* conditions. We found that norepinephrine, melatonin and insulin inhibited the growth of *C. jejuni* at 2 and 4 hours incubation. These repressor effects of hormones (except high-level norepinephrine and insulin) on bacterial growth were found to be disappeared when the incubation period was prolonged to 24 hours. Many studies showed that, norepinephrine altered the growth of different kinds of microorganisms (UPEC, EHEC, Salmonella, Shigella, Staphylococcus species, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *C. jejuni*, *E. faecalis*).^{22,23,27-29} Inconsistent with our findings, in some previous studies, the growth of *C. jejuni* was found to be increased in iron-limited conditions.^{12,30,31} In our study, hormones generally found to inhibit bacterial growth in a time-dependent manner.

Adhesion is the one of most important virulence factors of microorganisms which is defined as necessary for colonization and outcome of infection. The adhesion of various microorganisms (*C. albicans*, *E. coli*, *E. faecalis*, *S. pneumoniae*) in different cell cultures was found to be affected in response to mammalian hormones.³²⁻³⁴ It was shown that norepinephrine and epinephrine increased the adhesion of *C. jejuni* strain;^{12,31,35} while serotonin, corticosterone, cortisol and cortisone decreased the adhesion of *Campylobacter* isolates.^{8,12} In our study, it was found that all hormones at all concentrations decreased the adhesion of *C. jejuni* to

HT-29 cells.

Host hormones were shown to inhibit/increase different microorganisms' (UPEC, *C. albicans*, *Salmonella choleraesuis* and *E. coli* O157:H7) internalization/invasion process in various cell lines.^{7,36,37} For instance, the results from Xu et al.³¹ and Truccollo et al.¹² showed that norepinephrine, epinephrine, corticosterone, cortisol and cortisone increased the invasion of *C. jejuni*; whereas in other studies, norepinephrine and serotonin were reported to have no effect on invasion processes.^{8,38} Consistent with Aroori and Lyte's results^{8,38} in our study, all concentrations of norepinephrine, melatonin and estradiol were shown to not affect on invasion of *C. jejuni*. However, we found that progesterone and insulin increased the invasion of *C. jejuni* similar to findings of Edwards focused on *N. gonorrhoeae* and progesterone interactions.³⁹

It is well known that adhesion and invasion are defined as early stages of pathogenesis during infectious processes. In the present study, all concentrations of hormones were found to decrease the adhesion of *C. jejuni* and all concentrations of progesterone and insulin increased the invasion of bacteria. Inconsistency between adhesion and invasion can be due to independent efficiency of invasion mechanisms or biological properties of cell lines used for experiments.^{17,40,41}

During the infectious process, another important virulence factor is biofilm formation which provides

colonization of microbial populations avoiding the host's immune system, environmental stress conditions and antimicrobials. There are studies showing that host hormones affect in-vitro biofilm formation of EHEC, *E. faecalis*, *C. albicans* and *S. pneumoniae*.^{9,22,28,42} In the present study, we determined the ability of *C. jejuni* for adherence on abiotic surfaces in the presence of hormones. Biofilm formation of *C. jejuni* was decreased in the presence of norepinephrine (at two concentrations) and estradiol (at high concentration); increased in the presence of low-level melatonin, insulin (at low levels) and progesterone at two concentrations.

In a host, bacteria expose various environmental stress factors such as oxidative and nitrosative molecules. It is well known that these molecules are released by immune system cells to destroy microorganisms.^{17,43} Intarak et al.¹⁶ showed that epinephrine-treated *B. pseudomallei* cells were more resistant to paraquat (a superoxide generating agent) than the untreated control. Gao et al.⁴⁴ reported that norepinephrine up-regulated *sodB* gene expression which is defined as related to oxidative stress in *Aeromonas hydrophila*. Xu et al.³¹ reported that oxidative and nitrosative stress-related genes (*katA*, *Cj1386*, *Cj0466* and *Cj0379c-Cj0378c*) were downregulated when strain was treated with norepinephrine and epinephrine; while in epinephrine treated strain, hemerythrin *HerB* (*Cj1224*, *Cj1358c-Cj1357c*, *Cj0780/Cj0783* and *Cj1490c-Cj1488c*) which is involved in protecting from oxygen damage was reported to be upregulated. They suggested that epinephrine and norepinephrine provide increased tolerance to nitrosative and oxidative stress. In our study, the growth of *C. jejuni* was not affected by hydrogen peroxide and sodium nitroprusside in the presence/absence of hormones.

Previous studies have reported that hormones have protective/proliferative effects on different cell lines such as A549, HT-29, PA-1.^{24,45-48} All hormones at all concentrations were shown to decrease the viability of HT-29 cells in 24 hours. However, in 48 hours, low concentration of estradiol and high concentration of progesterone have increased the viability HT-29 cells. It seems that the effects of hormones were time and concentration-dependent. For instance, it is well known that HT-29 cell line consists of cancerous colonic mucosa cells with specific receptors for estrogen and progesterone.^{49,50} In this context, previous studies have shown that hormones cause different effects on cancer cell lines via altering many pathways.^{24,51,52}

It is well known that the infection affect the viabilities of infected cells. In this study, we found that the infection of HT-29 cells with *C. jejuni* has significant inhibitory effect on the viability of HT-29 cells in line with previous studies⁵³⁻⁵⁵ but only after incubation for 24 hours.

On the other hand, some studies showed that the effects of hormones on infected cells are due to the alterations of virulence properties of microorganisms by hormones. Thus, in the present study, we examined alterations of cell viability in the co-presence of hormones and *C. jejuni* in HT-29 cell culture. According to our results, the rates of viability were found to be variable. After incubation for 24 hours, we found that high levels of norepinephrine, estradiol, progesterone and low-level concentrations of melatonin and estradiol have enhanced the viabilities of infected HT-29 cells. Similarly, at 48 hours post-infection, we found that high-level concentrations of melatonin, estradiol and low-level concentrations of norepinephrine, estradiol and insulin have increased the viabilities of infected HT-29 cells. These effects of hormones on HT-29 cells infected with *C. jejuni* depend on dosage and time of exposure. In general, the alterations of the viability of HT-29 cells by hormones were found to be more significant in infected cells than non-infected cells. Due to the lack of studies showing the influences of hormones on *C. jejuni* infected cells, we could not compare our results.

In conclusion, the purpose of this study was to show how various host hormones may affect the pathogenicity of *C. jejuni* using methods mimicking *in vivo* conditions as closely as possible. There are previous studies focused on the effects of catecholamines on biological properties of *C. jejuni*.^{12,31} However, a lot is still to be learned about hormones and microbial interactions, concerning bi-directional communications. To our knowledge, this is the first study investigating the interactions between different host hormones and *C. jejuni* in cell culture. Our paper supported that, host hormones affected adhesion, invasion and biofilm formation processes independently from each other. Moreover, we suggest that experimental conditions such as hormone concentrations, exposing time, media used and biotic/abiotic surfaces are important for the evaluation of alterations on microorganisms' biological properties. To show the interactions between hormones and microorganisms more clearly, it is important to optimize *in vivo* conditions and focus on the effects of bidirectional communication between host cell receptors and microbial receptors which are regulated by presence/absence of host hormones.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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Περίληψη

The effects of mammalian hormones in the regulation of growth and virulence in *Campylobacter jejuni*

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Το βακτήριο *Campylobacter jejuni* αν και αποτελεί την πιο συχνή αιτία βακτηριακής τροφιμογενούς λοίμωξης, οι μελέτες σχετικά με την παθογένειά του εξακολουθούν να είναι περιορισμένες. Υπάρχουν αναφορές σχετικά με τις επιδράσεις διαφόρων ορμονών των θηλαστικών, όπως της νορεπινεφρίνης, της επινεφρίνης, της σεροτονίνης, της κορτικοστερόνης, της κορτιζόλης και της κορτιζόλης στην ανάπτυξη και στους διαφορετικούς μηχανισμούς λοιμογόνου δράσης του μικροβίου.

Στην παρούσα μελέτη διερευνήθηκαν οι πιθανές επιδράσεις της νορεπινεφρίνης, της μελατονίνης, της οιστραδιόλης, της προγεστερόνης και της ινσουλίνης στην ανάπτυξη, στην προσκόλληση και στην διείσδυση του *C. jejuni* σε σειρά κυττάρων του ανθρώπινου αδενοκαρκινώματος του παχέος εντέρου (HT-29). Επιπλέον, διερευνήθηκαν οι αλλαγές στο σχηματισμό βιομεμβράνης σε αβιοτικές επιφάνειες και η απόκριση σε συνθήκες στρες. Στόχος επίσης ήταν η ανάλυση των επιδράσεων των ορμονών και του *C. jejuni*, σε συνδυασμό ή χωριστά, στη βιωσιμότητα των κυττάρων HT-29. Οι μεταβολές της ανάπτυξης προσδιορίστηκαν φασματοφωτομετρικά. Οι μετρήσεις προσκόλλησης / διείσδυσης των βακτηρίων αξιολογήθηκαν με τη μέθοδο μέτρησης αποικιών. Ο σχηματισμός βιομεμβράνης αναλύθηκε χρησιμοποιώντας δοκιμασία πλάκας μικροτιτλοδότησης. Οι μεταβολές της βιωσιμότητας των κυττάρων HT-29 προσδιορίστηκαν μέσω δοκιμασίας βρωμιούχου μεθυλ-θειαζολυλ διφαινυλ-τετραζολίου.

Σύμφωνα με τα αποτελέσματα μας, η ανάπτυξη του βακτηρίου *C. jejuni* μειώθηκε παρουσία ορμονών με τρόπο εξαρτόμενο από τη δόση και το χρόνο ($p < 0,05$). Κάθε ορμόνη, σε όλες τις συγκεντρώσεις μείωσε την προσκόλληση των βακτηρίων ($p < 0,0001$). Η διείσδυση του βακτηρίου *C. jejuni* αυξήθηκε παρουσία προγεστερόνης και ινσουλίνης σε όλες τις συγκεντρώσεις σε στατιστικά σημαντικό βαθμό ($p < 0,0001$). Οι επιδράσεις των ορμονών στο σχηματισμό βιομεμβράνης ήταν ποικίλες. Οι ορμόνες δεν επηρέασαν την ανάπτυξη του βακτηρίου *C. jejuni* σε οξειδωτικό και νιτρωτικό στρες ($p > 0,05$). Κάθε ορμόνη και λοίμωξη από *C. jejuni* έχουν μειώσει χωριστά τη βιωσιμότητα των κυττάρων μετά από 24 ώρες επώασης ($p < 0,005$). Σε 48 ώρες, η βιωσιμότητα των κυττάρων αυξήθηκε σημαντικά παρουσία οιστραδιόλης χαμηλού επιπέδου ($p < 0,0001$) και υψηλού επιπέδου προγεστερόνης ($p < 0,0005$). Οι ορμόνες βρέθηκαν να είναι σημαντικά πιο αποτελεσματικές στη βιωσιμότητα των μολυσμένων κυττάρων HT-29 από τα μη μολυσμένα κύτταρα.

Συμπερασματικά, αυτά τα ευρήματα έδειξαν για άλλη μια φορά ότι οι ορμόνες επηρεάζουν το *C. jejuni* κατά τη διάρκεια μολυσματικών διεργασιών.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

Campylobacter jejuni, ορμόνες θηλαστικών, ανάπτυξη, προσκόλληση-διείσδυση, κύτταρο παχέος εντέρου, βιομεμβράνη

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